

Synthesis of 4-Arylazo-1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-arylamino-pyrazole Derivatives and their Application as Disperse Dyes. Part-III†

MOHAMED ABBAS METWALLY*, YASSIN M. DARWISH, MAGDY M. EL-HUSSINI and FATHY A. AMER

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Mansoura, Mansoura, Egypt

Manuscript received 4 June 1987, accepted 2 December 1987

Nucleophilic substitution reaction of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-arylazo-5-chloropyrazoles (1) with ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate and/or *p*-aminophenol resulted in the formation of 5-arylamino-pyrazoles 2a-c and 8a-l. Interaction of 2a with hydrazine hydrate gave 3, which underwent condensation with *p*-anisaldehyde to give the hydrazone 7. Reaction of 3 with phenyl isothiocyanate afforded 4 which on cyclisation with NaOH/1, and/or NaOH gave 5 and 6. While the reaction of 8 with monochloroacetic acid and/or ethyl chloroacetate gave the phenoxyacetic acids (9a-e) and the phenoxyacetates (10a-e), respectively. Cyclisation of 9c and/or 10c with sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of 11. Condensation of 8 with ethyl acetoacetate gave the chromenones (12a-e). The Riemer-Tiemann reaction of 8 with chloroform resulted in the formation of 13a-e which underwent condensation with diethylmalonate and/or ethyl acetoacetate to give 14a-e and 15a-e, respectively. The validity of the compounds 8a-e, 12a-e, 14a-e and 15a-e as disperse dyes for dyeing polyester fibre and their fastness properties towards washing, rubbing, acid-alkaline perspiration and light were investigated.

In continuation of our studies on the preparation of 4-arylazopyrazoles¹ and 4-arylhya-zono-2-pyrazolin-5-ones²⁻⁵ and their application as dyes⁶⁻⁸ of commercial value, this work describes the preparation of some new 4-arylazo-1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-arylamino-pyrazole derivatives. The usefulness of these compounds as disperse dyes was investigated.

In a previous work¹, we reported the preparation of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-arylazo-5-chloropyrazoles (1). It has been reported that 5-chloropyrazoles with an electron-withdrawing group (e.g. phenylazo) at C-4 have the chlorine activated towards nucleophilic aromatic substitution⁹. The present work using compounds 1 confirms and extends this finding. Thus ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate with 1 yields the corresponding crystalline 5-aminopyrazoles (2a-c). These amines could exist in four possible tautomeric forms⁹: A, the N-2 H form; B, the chelated hydrazone; C, the C-4 H form; D, the amine. Previous work has shown that Raman spectra exhibited a band at 1 385 cm⁻¹ which is consistent with the chelated amine form D or with the hydrazone form B. Ir spectra showed the following characteristic bands: (i) a sharp band at 3 400-3 200 cm⁻¹ assigned for the sym. vibrations of NH, such band is at much lower frequency than the typical NH due to the possibility for hydrogen bonding, (ii) a sharp and intense band at 1 710-1 695 cm⁻¹ assigned for C=O sym. stretching vibrations of the ester group, in addition to a clear and sharp band at 830 cm⁻¹ assigned for OEt sym. stretching vibration and (iii) a band of medium intensity at 1 650-1 620 cm⁻¹ assigned for the C=N.

Further evidence for the formation of 2 was gained from the mass spectra, which showed an M⁺ at 439 (2a) fitting exactly with the obtained molecular weight.

†Refs. 6,7.

Condensation of **2a** with hydrazine hydrate, gave the hydrazide (**3**) which underwent addition with phenyl isothiocyanate to give the thiocarbamate (**4**). The structure of **3** was based on satisfactory analytical data; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400 (NH₂), 3 300 (NH) and 1 700 cm⁻¹ (CO); δ 2.25 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 4.25 (2H, m, NH₂), 6.6 (1H, m, CONH), 7-8 (13H, m, ArH) and 8.3 (1H, s, NHAr); m/z M⁺ 425. In the ir spectra of **4**, a new band due to C=S was noticed at 1 105 cm⁻¹.

The thiocarbamate (**4**) underwent cyclisation with sodium hydroxide solution and iodine to give the oxadiazole (**5**), and with sodium hydroxide to give **6**. Most of the absorption bands disappeared in the cyclised product **5** and the NH absorption was recorded at 3 190 cm⁻¹.

Reaction of *p*-anisaldehyde with the hydrazide (**3**) yields the hydrazone (**7**) as inferred from its correct analytical data; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 250 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 650 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.2 (3H, s, methylpyrazole), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.15 (1H, s, CONH), 6.5-7.9 (17H, m, ArH), 8.35 (1H, s, N=CH) and 8.5 (1H, s, NHAr). Further evidence for the formation of **7** was gained from its mass spectra, which gave an M⁺ 543, fitting exactly with the obtained molecular weight.

The validity of the chloropyrazoles (**1**) towards the nucleophilic substitution reaction with ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate, prompted us to extend this finding. Thus, treatment of **1** with *p*-aminophenol gave the arylaminopyrazoles (**8a-1**). Reaction of **8** with monochloroacetic acid and/or ethyl chloroacetate affords the phenoxyacetic acids (**9a-e**) and the

corresponding phenoxy acetate (**10a-e**), respectively. The ir spectra of **9** showed $\nu_{\max}$ 1 270

(OCH₂), 1 600 (C=N), 1 650 and 1 380 ($\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{O} \end{matrix}$),

1 700 (C=O of COOH), 3 200 (NH) and 3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH of COOH). Cyclisation of **9c** or **10c** with sulphuric acid afforded the benzofuran derivative (**11**).

Confirmatory evidence for the formation of **11** was gained from ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 735 (C=O) and 3 350 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.25 (3H, s, H₃CC=N), 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 3.6 (2H, m, COCH₂O cyclic) and 7-8 (12H, m, ArH). In the mass spectra of **11** no molecular ion was noticed, but the observed fragment m/z 275 corresponding to C₁₇H₁₅N₄, was obviously formed by the loss of the benzofuranyl fragment from the parent ion.

Condensation of **8** with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of the chromenone derivatives (**12a-e**) as inferred from their satisfactory analytical and spectral data.

In connection with the above condensations, the Riemer-Tiemann reaction of 5-(*p*-hydroxyanilino)-1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(arylaazo)pyrazole (**1**) resulted in the formation of the salicylaldehyde derivatives (**13a-e**). The ir spectra of **13** showed bands at 3 500-3 300 (H-bonded OH), 1 650 (C=O aldehyde) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Reaction of **13** with diethyl malonate or ethyl acetoacetate in presence of piperidine gave chromenones **14a-e** and **15a-e**, respectively. The ir spectra of **14e** showed bands at 1 670 (CO ester), 1 720 (CO pyrone) and 3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH). The ¹H nmr

spectra of 14d displayed signals at δ 1.3 (3H, s, H₃CC=N), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.5 and 4.0 (5H, m, CH₂CH₂), 5.65 (1H, s, olefinic), 8.3 (1H, s, NH) and 7.2–8 (12H, m, ArH). The formation of 15 finds support from their satisfactory analytical and spectral data; the ir spectra showed absorption bands at 1 665–1 690, 1 695–1 705 (carbonyl side chain and pyrone) and 3 190–3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH).

5-Arylamino-pyrazole dyes: Representative compounds (8a–l, 12a–e, 13a–e, 14a–e and 15a–e) were tested as azo disperse dyes for dyeing polyester fibre using the carrier (*o*-phenylphenol)^{10,11} dyeing process. In general, they have good substantivity to the fibre affording yellow to orange shades and having satisfactory fastness to washing (4.5), rubbing (3), acid and alkaline perspiration and to light fastness (Table 1).

Conclusion: From the results (Table 1) we can predict that the introduction of the methoxyl group shows a noticeable visual change in the brightness of colour, while the introduction of the nitro group deepens the colour and enhances the light fastness. On the other hand, the combination of the chromone ring and the methoxyl group in the chemical structure of 12, 14 and 15 has a reasonable effect on the colour hue.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Fisher–Johns melting point apparatus and are uncorrected.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2a–c AND 3–7

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p. °C	Yield %	Formula (Mol. wt.)
2a	Brown	158	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ (439.50)
2b	Yellow	152	79	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl (459.92)
2c	Reddish brown	154	82	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ (455.5)
3	Brown	186	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (425.47)
4	Brown	65	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ SO (560.66)
5	Brown	100	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (526.59)
6	Brown yellowish	153	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S (542.65)
7	Brown	139	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ (543.60)
8a	Black	95	80	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (369.41)
8b	Brown	130	75	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (383.44)
8c	Black	170	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (383.44)
8d	Dark brown	189	85	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (383.44)
8e	Brown yellow	118	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ OCl (403.85)
8f	Brown yellow	121	76	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ OCl (403.85)
8g	Dark brown	158	75	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ OCl (403.85)
8h	Black	123	68	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ (399.44)
8i	Dark violet	204	78	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ (399.44)

(Table 1 contd.)

8j	Brown	188	82	$C_{22}H_{19}N_5O_2$ (399.44)
8k	Dark brown	185	82	$C_{22}H_{19}N_5O_2$ (414.41)
8l	Brown	159	80	$C_{22}H_{19}N_5O_2$ (414.41)
9a	Brown	88	80	$C_{24}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (427.45)
9b	Brown	110	82	$C_{22}H_{19}N_5O_2$ (441.47)
9c	Black	> 290	80	$C_{22}H_{19}N_5O_2$ (441.47)
9d	Brown	160	90	$C_{25}H_{21}N_5O_4$ (457.47)
9e	Dark brown	157	86	$C_{25}H_{21}N_5O_4$ (457.47)
10a	Dark brown	96	80	$C_{26}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (455.50)
10b	Black	—	75	$C_{27}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (469.53)
10c	Black	115	76	$C_{27}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (469.53)
10d	Dark brown	—	81	$C_{27}H_{23}N_5O_4$ (485.53)
10e	Black	280	90	$C_{27}H_{23}N_5O_4$ (485.53)
11	Black	> 290	58	$C_{25}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (423.46)
12a	Grey	130	60	$C_{26}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (435.47)
12b	Yellowish grey	105	72	$C_{27}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (449.49)
12c	Brown	205	79	$C_{27}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (449.49)
12d	Dark brown	112	73	$C_{27}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (465.49)
12e	Black	165	76	$C_{27}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (465.49)
13a	Dark brown	150	81	$C_{28}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (397.42)
13b	Yellow	160	78	$C_{28}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (411.45)
13c	Brown	108	69	$C_{28}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (411.45)
13d	Brown	135	68	$C_{28}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (427.45)
13e	Dark brown	162	75	$C_{28}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (427.45)
14a	Black	105	86	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (493.5)
14b	Brown	83	82	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (507.53)
14c	Yellow	96	70	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (507.53)
14d	Brown	162	88	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (523.53)
14e	Brown	100	85	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (523.53)
15a	Brown	78	71	$C_{27}H_{21}N_5O_2$ (463.48)
15b	Orange	85	75	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (477.5)
15c	Yellow	98	81	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (477.5)
15d	Black	150	78	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (493.5)
15e	Brown	110	68	$C_{29}H_{23}N_5O_2$ (493.5)

*Elementary analyses of all compounds gave satisfactory.

Microanalyses of carbon and hydrogen were done at Microanalytical Laboratory, Faculty of Science, University of Mansoura. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer, 1H nmr spectra determined on a Varian

XL 100 spectrometer and mass spectra measured using AET MS-9 spectrophotometer at 70 eV. The analytical and physical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1. Polyester fibre was used to assess the dyeing behaviour of the compounds (Table 2). All application and fastness properties of the dyes were made at El-Nasr Spinning, Weaving and Dyeing Company, Mehalla El-Kobra, Egypt.

5-(p-Carboethoxyanilino)-1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(aryla-azo)pyrazoles (2a-c): In a 25 cm³ round-bottom flask, fitted with an air condenser, the chloropyrazoles (1; 0.001 mol) were mixed with ethyl *p*-aminobenzoate (0.001 mol). The reaction mixture was fused by heating the flask in an oil-bath at 140° for 4–6 h, and then the mixture was cooled. The product obtained in each case was crystallised from benzene–petroleum ether (b.p. 80–100°) mixture.

Condensation of 2a with hydrazine hydrate. Formation of the hydrazide 3: A mixture of 2a (0.001 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.002 mol) in dry ethanol (50 cm³) was heated under reflux (steam-bath) for 5 h. The product obtained on cooling, was filtered off, crystallised from benzene–petroleum ether (b.p. 80–100°) mixture to give brown crystals of 3 (Table 1).

Condensation of 3 with phenyl isothiocyanate. Formation of the thiocarbamate (4): To a solution of 3 (0.002 mol) in ethanol (60 cm³) was added phenyl isothiocyanate (0.002 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The separated product on cooling was filtered and crystallised from benzene–petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) mixture to give brown crystals of 4 (Table 1).

Cyclisation of 4 with sodium hydroxide and iodine. Formation of 5: The thiocarbamate (4; 0.001 mol) was dissolved in cold solution of sodium hydroxide (4 N, 5 cm³). Iodine solution (5%) was then added dropwise with stirring till the colour of iodine persisted. The mixture was refluxed and more iodine solution was added till a permanent tinge of iodine remained. The mixture was then cooled and treated with ice-cold water. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with dilute Na₂S₂O₃ solution and then with water and crystallised from ethanol to give brown crystals of 5 (Table 1).

Cyclisation of 4 with sodium hydroxide. Formation of 5: The thiocarbamate (4; 0.001 mol) and sodium hydroxide solution (2 N, 10 cm³) were refluxed for 3 h. The solution was then cooled, filtered and acidified with acetic acid. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol to give brown-yellow crystals of 6 (Table 1).

Condensation of 4 with p-anisaldehyde. Formation of the Schiff base (7): A mixture of 4 (0.001 mol), *p*-anisaldehyde (0.001 mol) in ethanol (50 cm³) containing acetic acid (1 cm³) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid product that separated on cooling was filtered off, crystallised from benzene–petroleum

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF DYING OF POLYESTER FIBRE USING THE ARYLAMINOPYRAZOLES 8a-1, 12a-e, 13a-e 14a-e AND 15a-e

Compd. no.	Dyed sample 2% depth	Fastness property										Light fastness after 80 h
		Washing		Rubbing		Acid perspiration			Alkaline perspiration			
		Colour change	Staining on cotton	Wet	Dry	Colour change	Staining on cotton	Staining on wool	Colour change	Staining on cotton	Staining on wool	
8a	Pale grey	4	5	1	2	4	5	5	4	5	5	6-7
b	Yellowish grey	4-5	5	1	2	4	5	5	4	5	5	6-7
c	Grey	4-5	5	1	3	4-5	5	5	4-5	5	5	6-7
d	Pale grey	4-5	5	3	4-5	4	5	5	4	5	5	7
e	Yellowish grey	4	5	1-2	2-3	4-5	5	5	4-5	5	5	7
f	Pale yellow	4-5	5	4	4-5	4	5	5	4	5	5	7
g	Pale violet	3-4	4	1-2	2-3	3-4	5	5	3-4	5	5	6-7
h	Golden yellow	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
i	Yellowish grey	4	5	2-3	3-4	3-4	5	5	3-4	5	5	7
j	Yellowish grey	5	4	2	2-3	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
k	Yellowish grey	4-5	5	3-4	4	4	5	5	4	5	5	7
l	Brown	5	5	2-3	3-4	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
12a	Pale yellow	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
b	Pale yellow	5	5	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
c	Yellowish grey	4-5	5	2	2	3-4	5	5	3-4	5	5	6-7
d	Lemon yellow	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	8
e	Yellow	5	5	2	2-3	4	5	5	4	5	5	6
13a	Yellow	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
b	Deep yellow	5	5	2-3	3-4	5	5	5	5	5	5	6-7
c	Deep yellow	5	5	3-4	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	5	6
d	Yellow	5	5	3-4	4-5	4-5	5	5	4-5	5	5	6
e	Golden yellow	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
14a	Pale yellow	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	4	5	5	7
b	Golden yellow	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
c	Pale yellow	4	5	2-3	4-5	4	5	5	4	5	5	6
d	Lemon yellow	4-5	5	3-4	2-3	3-4	5	5	3-4	5	5	6-7
e	Yellowish grey	4	5	1	3	4	5	5	4	5	5	6
15a	Yellow	5	5	4-5	5	4-5	5	5	4-5	5	5	6-7
b	Golden yellow	5	5	4	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
c	Lemon yellow	5	5	4	4-5	5	5	5	5	5	5	7
d	Deep yellow	4-5	5	3	4	4	5	5	4	5	5	6-7
e	Pale yellow	4	5	4	5	3-4	5	5	3-4	5	5	6-7

ether (b.p. 60–80°) mixture to give brown crystals of 7 (Table 1).

5-(p-Hydroxyanilino)-1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles (8a-1): The compounds were synthesised in the same manner as reported for 2, from 1 (0.001 mol) and *p*-aminophenol (0.001 mol) to give solid products 8a-1, crystallised from dilute ethanol (Table 1).

Condensation of 8 with monochloroacetic acid. Formation of 9a-e: To a mixture of 8 (1 g) and 33% sodium hydroxide solution (4 cm³), 50% monochloroacetic acid (30 cm³) was added, followed by addition of water (50 cm³). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h, then diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid products that separated were filtered off and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Ethyl phenoxyacetate derivatives (10a-e): A mixture of 8 (0.01 mol), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (7 g) and dry acetone (200 ml) was heated for 30 min. Ethyl chloroacetate was added to the refluxing solution and further refluxed for 24 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue poured into ice. The solid products that separated were filtered off and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Cyclisation of 9c and/or 10c with concentrated H₂SO₄. Formation of 11: To 9c or 10c (2 g) was added 70% H₂SO₄ (25 cm³), refluxed for 2h, cooled, and diluted with water. The precipitated product was washed several times with water, filtered off and crystallised from aqueous ethanol to give compound 11.

Condensation of 8 with ethyl acetoacetate. Formation of 12a-e: To a mixture of 8 (0.01 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.011 mol), 70% H₂SO₄ (25 cm³) was added dropwise while cold. The reaction mixture was set aside at room temperature for 24 h and then poured into ice-cold water. The solid product that separated was filtered off, washed several times with water and crystallised from ethanol.

Riemer-Tiemann reaction of 8. Formation of 13a-e: A solution of sodium hydroxide (40 g in 80 cm³ water) was added to a solution of 8 (0.14 mol) in 95% ethanol (60 cm³) with stirring. Then chloroform (0.02 mol) was added dropwise to the reaction mixture at 70–80° and stirring was continued for 1 h after all the chloroform was added. The water and ethanol were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was acidified with 0.1 N hydrochloric acid and crystallised from ethanol.

Condensation of 13 with diethyl malonate and/or ethyl acetoacetate. Formation of the chromenones 14a-e and 15a-e: To a mixture of 13 (0.001 mol) and diethyl malonate or ethyl acetoacetate (0.0011 mol), a few drops of piperidine in ethanol (30 cm³) were added. The reaction mixture was set aside at room temperature for 15 days. The solid product that separated was filtered off and crystallised from ethanol.

References

1. M. A. METWALLY, Y. M. DARWISH and F. A. AMER, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1987, communicated (mss. no. 000).
2. M. A. METWALLY and F. A. AMER, *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1981, **24**, 135.
3. M. A. METWALLY and F. A. AMER, *Pharmazie*, 1983, **38**, 172.
4. M. A. METWALLY and F. A. AMER, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 316.
5. M. A. METWALLY, M. Y. YOUSIF, A. M. ISMAIEL and F. A. AMER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 52.
6. F. A. AMER, T. ZIMAITY and A. M. METWALLY, *J. Appl. Chem. Biotechnol.*, 1978, **28**, 560.
7. F. A. AMER, E. S. AYSAH and M. SOAFAN, *J. Appl. Chem. Biotechnol.*, 1980, **30**, 78.
8. A. A. FADDA, M. A. METWALLY and A. M. KHALIL, *Indian J. Text.*, 1983, **8**, 82.
9. E. M. E. EID, T. G. BONNER and D. LEWIS, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1983, **20**, 1501.
10. E. R. FRIESER, and U. ZELLWOLLE, *Chemiefasern.*, 1959, **9**, 378.
11. T. M. RALDWINSON, *J. Soc. Dyer Colour*, 1971, **44**, 246.